

GREEK TERMINOLOGY MEANING THERAPEUTIC AND SURGICAL METHODS OF TREATMENT. GREEK AND LATIN DUPLICATED NAMES

Abdusalimov Sukhrob Rustamovich

Assistent Teacher of the Department of Languages, Samarkand State Medical University

Abdur Rehman

The 1 st year student of International Faculty, Samarkand State Medical University

Abstract. This article discusses the meaning of Greek and Latin terms in therapeutic and surgical disease designations, methods of application, forms of anatomical and clinical doublets in Greek and Latin.

Key words: designation, application, therapeutic, terms, interpretation, idiom, catastrophe, anesthesia

There is hardly any other aspect of that is so discouraging and discomfoting for the medical students for which they have to study about a thousand words of surgical terms therapeutic terms and etc. which they have to study in both languages Greek and Latin also the meaning, structure, vocabulary, gender and stem and etc. This side of the medical education journey of the student maybe a little bit difficult but also fun at the same time where they will learn that these are actually interesting and intriguing. A French essayist of the 16th century made the apt remark saying that “the language of medicine is an idiom foreign to the general speech and discordant sounds”. So basically what he’s trying to say is in the opinion of my interpretation of the phrase is that the

language of medicine which is Greek and Latin are spoken by almost all the professionals in this field like doctors, nurses, physicians etc. are difficult to be understood by the general public who aren't in the medical field is hard to understand, also the languages Greek and Latin are not spoke in like a general Greek man or a Latin speaking person, only the clinical, surgical, therapeutically terms are spoken by the professionals in the field. Where they use this terms to determine the disease, to diagnose and also in the surgical field. To determine they position of the incision in surgery surgeon's use words like anterior, posterior, inferior, to determine the position of the incision and also where to start applying the lines for the IV and whatnot.

Although medical terms have been drawn from many languages but majority are drawn from Greek and Latin because these are one of the very first to propose these terms and many historical figures have hailed from these lands where they are considered father of medicine for examples Hippocrates. Some familiarity with the meaning of the most frequent used roots, stem, gender etc. with a little bit of hard work in studying these words we can clearly see that some of the formidable sounding medical terms and whole lot of terms are a combination of words which describe the body part, a function meaning what these part is responsible which in turn means for example like what does the heart do and what do the arm do or the lungs for that matter, or a condition where the patient is ill with a unknown disease but can be diagnosed by these terms.

The most basic terms and the easiest ones are always repeated over and over again in various and easy combination we just have to learn how to put these words together and what goes with what and we can easily learn how to use these words then it will be easy to speak in the language of medicine which is an accomplishment where an general individual will find it difficult and struggle to complete.

The knowledge of the meaning of the roots, stem, gender, suffixes and prefixes enables the student to analyze and examine the words into component parts. This is of the greatest and the most meaning full help in learning to understand, speak the language of the medicine which is most required for the individual who is present in the medical field because when the senior doctors, physicians, nurses etc. speak in this format the individual might not understand and misinterpret which will cause miscommunication which in turn will lead to major catastrophe which will lead the misdiagnose or even worse in death for the patient.

Which is why learning lasting and Greek terms are critically essential for the individual to learn and understand and read the language of the medicine. Some of the names of the body parts for example anatomy which is derived from Latin meaning the body parts are derived centuries ago which are still used in day to day life in the medical field. For example words like amigo, cardio, and encephalon are the Latin words for

arteries, heard and brain in Latin, these words are still used till now in the modern 21st century. It is said that three-fourths of the medical terminology that are used in this field are from the Greek language.

The most prominent reason for why Greek words are dominant in the terms around the worlds where they don't even speak this language is because the Greeks were the founding fathers of the rational medicine.

Most of the things that we know of are already done by the Greeks which is why they hold responsible for owning most of the words and terms and this is also preferred to be used around the world. This all happened in the golden age of civilization. In the 5th century the school of Hippocrates who is considered still to this day the father of medicine. Where he ran a school names the The Hippocratic School and later on Galen, These places formulated theories which was used up and until the point of 18th century.

The people who were studying in his institution and those who were also working were the first to describe diseases based observation, which means that they observed what ails the sick person and could make an apt observation which were founded by these people who were working in the Hippocratic School. And they also coined many terms for example arthritis, nephritis, pleurisies, which in turn means joint pain, pain in the kidney and pain in the pleura which is the covering of the heart muscle which helps to contract and pass electricity which helps in the rhythmic contraction of the heart which in turn helps to pump the blood to the body. Here are some of the examples for the greek surgical terminologies which are still used in the modern day medicine.

1. Chirurgia (Χειρουργία): Surgery
2. Anesthesia (Αναισθησία): Anesthesia
3. Hemostasis (Αιμόσταση): Control of bleeding
4. Antiseptikos (Αντισηπτικός): Antiseptic
5. Asepsis (Ασηψία): Absence of germs or microorganisms
6. Biopsy (Βιοψία): Removal and examination of tissue for diagnostic purposes
7. Laparoskopia (Λαπαροσκοπία): Laparoscopy
8. Osteotomy (Οστεοτομία): Surgical cutting of bone
9. Dermatoplasty (Δερματοπλαστική): Skin grafting
- Osteotomy (Οστεοτομία): Surgical cutting of bone
- Dermatoplasty (Δερματοπλαστική): Skin grafting
- Angioplasty (Αγγειοπλαστική): Surgical repair or unblocking of a blood vessel
- Orthopedics (Ορθοπαιδική): Branch of surgery dealing with the skeletal system and related structures
- Suture (Ραφή): Stitching or sewing tissues together
- Gastrostomia (Γαστροστομία): Surgical creation of an opening into the stomach through the abdominal wall
- Neurochirurgia (Νευροχειρουργική): Neurosurgery
- Cauterize (Καυτηριάζω): To burn or sear tissue with a hot instrument or caustic substance
- Tracheostomia (Τραχεοστομία): Surgical procedure to create an opening in the windpipe (trachea)
- Ligament (Δέσμη): A band of fibrous tissue that connects bones to other bones
- Tendon (Τένον): A fibrous tissue that connects muscle to bone
- Hernia (Κήλη): Protrusion of an organ through the wall of the cavity that normally contains it
- Prosthesis (Πρόθεση): Artificial body part or device to replace a missing or damaged body part.

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